

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT INNOVATION, SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING, AND LOCATION ON PURCHASE DECISIONS AT TEH POCI GANA (A Case Study of Teh Poci Gana in Bantul, Yogyakarta)

Nyoman Parartha Deswara Evaganna¹, Putu Saroyini Piartrini²

^{1,2}Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University

Corresponding author email: pararthadeswara001@gmail.com¹

Abstract

The background of this study is based on the phenomenon of a significant decline in the sales turnover of Teh Poci Gana due to intense competition from similar businesses within its operational area. This study aims to examine and explain the influence of product innovation, social media marketing, and location on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. The research was conducted at Teh Poci Gana located in Dusun Ngebel, Tamantirto, Bantul Regency, Yogyakarta. This study employs a quantitative approach with an associative research design. The population consists of all consumers who have previously purchased products from Teh Poci Gana. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, involving 200 respondents. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis, classical assumption tests, and hypothesis testing (t-test and F-test) with the assistance of SPSS version 25. The results show that: (1) product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions, indicating that better product innovation leads to higher consumer purchase decisions; (2) social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions, suggesting that effective promotion through social media can increase purchase decisions; and (3) location has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions, where ease of access and visibility significantly contribute to consumers' purchasing decisions. Simultaneously, these three independent variables have a significant effect on purchase decisions, with a contribution of 23.3%.

Keywords: Product Innovation, Social Media Marketing, Location, Purchase Decision, Teh Poci Gana.

INTRODUCTION

Teh Poci Gana is one of the iced tea beverage vendors located on Jalan Rajawali, Dusun Ngebel, Tamantirto Village, Kasihan District, Bantul Regency, Yogyakarta. This business was established in February 2023 and currently has three branches with a total of seven employees supporting its operations. Teh Poci Gana is owned by Nyoman Parartha Deswara Evaganna, and its name is inspired by the owner. Starting with strong determination and simple market research, Teh Poci Gana has been able to meet market demands in its selling area, particularly in Dusun Ngebel.

The business offers high-quality iced tea in portable plastic cups, affordable prices, a wide variety of flavors, and a strategic location close to consumers, particularly students of Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta. Additionally, it utilizes the well-known Teh Cap Poci brand, which has long been recognized in Yogyakarta and across Indonesia. These factors contribute to consumers' purchase decisions. Supported by the long-established taste of Teh Cap Poci, Teh Poci Gana also innovates by adding

flavored powders to its menu, including fruit, milk, coffee, and other variants, thereby creating added value in competing with existing competitors.

The increasing number of franchise tea beverage businesses offering similar products and prices in Dusun Ngebel has intensified competition for Teh Poci Gana. The emergence of new competitors has led to a decline in sales turnover (Dana & Suci, 2021), as consumers now have more alternatives and may switch to competitors. Within a 500-meter radius, there are nine competitors selling tea-based beverages, such as Teh Desa, Teh Tarik Bakar, Teh Impian, Teh Tarik Jodi, Fremilt, Blended, Teh Juara, and Teh Mimpi.

The presence of new competitors in close proximity poses a significant challenge for the business. These competitors offer similar products, competitive pricing strategies, and comparable marketing tactics, forcing companies to enhance their efforts to remain competitive. This phenomenon can be effectively analyzed using the S-O-R (Stimulus-Organism-Response) theory.

This theory considers the presence of competitors and their strategies as external stimuli (S). These stimuli, such as lower prices or attractive advertising, influence the organism (O), namely consumers' thoughts and feelings. Consumers then compare different products and brands, process information, and form perceptions. This internal process ultimately leads to a response (R), which is the actual consumer behavior either purchasing from Teh Poci Gana or switching to another seller. Therefore, Teh Poci Gana must understand and influence consumer perceptions through more effective strategies to drive purchase decisions.

One of Teh Poci Gana's main competitors is Es Teh Desa, which is considered the most influential and competitive rival due to its similar products and pricing. For instance, its main product, Jasmine Tea, is sold at a lower price compared to Teh Poci Gana Rp2,500 for a 22oz cup, while Teh Poci Gana sells a 16oz cup for Rp3,000. In addition to the main product, Teh Poci Gana has developed other best-selling variants through product innovation.

One such innovation is the matcha series introduced in February 2025, combining jasmine tea with matcha powder, resulting in a unique blend of sweet, rich, and slightly astringent flavors, with optional additions such as condensed milk and cocoa powder. However, from its launch until September 2025, this variant has not significantly increased sales turnover, as the number of units sold remains relatively low and shows no consistent growth over time.

In terms of social media performance, Teh Poci Gana's Instagram account has fewer followers than Teh Tarik Jodi but more than Teh Desa UMY. However, in terms of total content views, Teh Poci Gana lags behind both competitors, with only 15,000 total views compared to 35,000 and 70,000 views, respectively. Despite having visually appealing and informative content, lower exposure limits its effectiveness. Frequent exposure to promotional content on social media can influence purchase decisions (Hanaysha, 2022), and increased user engagement also plays a significant role (Ardiansyah & Sarwoko, 2020).

Location is another critical factor, as companies must determine how to deliver value effectively to target consumers (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018:78). A strategic location positively influences purchase decisions (Patmawati & Widow, 2023), as consumers prefer businesses that offer convenience and accessibility (Sari & Hidayat,

2020). Teh Poci Gana operates through physical stores and currently has three strategically located branches along main roads frequently accessed by students and local residents. Each branch is well-lit, equipped with promotional banners, and located approximately 500 meters apart, allowing broader market coverage. Compared to competitors with only one branch in the same area, Teh Poci Gana demonstrates superior distribution through strategic location selection.

Previous studies, such as those by Rayi and Aras (2021), Damayanti et al. (2023), and Septiani and Arini (2024), have shown that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Similarly, studies by Wikantari (2022), Ardiansyah and Sarwoko (2020), and Hanaysha (2022) confirm that social media marketing positively influences purchase decisions. High interaction, informative content, relevance, and entertainment value strengthen consumers' purchasing intentions. Additionally, a strategic location has also been found to significantly influence purchase decisions (Febrianto & Sumaryanto, 2024; Patmawati & Widow, 2023; Anhar et al., 2024).

Based on the product advantages, promotional strategies, and location factors of Teh Poci Gana, as well as the observed phenomena, this study entitled "The Influence of Product Innovation, Social Media Marketing, and Location on Purchase Decisions at Teh Poci Gana (A Case Study in Bantul, Yogyakarta)" is important to conduct.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative design with a survey approach to examine the influence of product innovation, social media marketing, and location on the purchase decisions of Teh Poci Gana consumers. The research was conducted in Dusun Ngebel, Tamantirto Village, Kasihan District, Bantul Regency, Special Region of Yogyakarta, which represents the operational area of all Teh Poci Gana outlets.

The object of this study focuses on consumer purchase decision behavior, while the research subjects are individuals who have made at least one purchase. The independent variables consist of product innovation, social media marketing, and location, whereas the dependent variable is purchase decision. Each variable is measured using relevant indicators, including product evaluation, trust, product creativity, digital content quality, and location accessibility (Anggadwita et al., 2019; Wijaya & Defrizal, 2024; Feny Indrawati et al., 2023; Febrianto & Sumaryanto, 2024).

The population of this study includes all consumers of Teh Poci Gana who have made purchases, which is considered infinite. The sample was determined using a non-probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling method, targeting respondents who had made a purchase within the last three months and had at least a high school level of education. Based on the sample size requirements for multivariate research (5–10 times the number of indicators), a total of 200 respondents were obtained.

The data used consist of both qualitative and quantitative data derived from primary sources (questionnaires and internal company data) and secondary sources (scientific literature). Data collection was conducted through the distribution of questionnaires both online and offline, utilizing a five-point Likert scale to measure

respondents' perceptions of the research variables (Sugiyono, 2017; Sfenrianto et al., 2018).

The research instrument was tested using validity and reliability tests to ensure measurement feasibility, with the results indicating that all indicators are valid ($MSA > 0.5$) and reliable (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.60). Data analysis was performed using SPSS software through classical assumption tests, including normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests, to ensure that the regression model meets statistical requirements. Furthermore, hypothesis testing was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis to determine the effect of each independent variable on purchase decisions. This regression model was used to predict changes in purchase decisions based on variations in product innovation, social media marketing, and location (Ningsih & Dukalang, 2019; Sugiyono, 2017).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Company Overview

Teh Poci Gana is a franchise partnership operating under the trademark license of Teh Poci, owned by PT Gunung Slamet, which has a strong reputation in the national tea industry. This business was established by Nyoman Parartha Deswara Evaganna in February 2023 and is located on Jalan Rajawali, Bantul, Special Region of Yogyakarta. It aims to capture market opportunities in the ready-to-drink beverage sector, which has consistently high and stable demand among local consumers.

The existence of Teh Poci Gana is grounded in its commitment to delivering high-quality products that comply with the standard operating procedures (SOP) established by the principal company, while also contributing positively to the microeconomic dynamics within its operational area.

In its business operations, Teh Poci Gana focuses on providing a variety of freshly brewed tea-based beverages, including original tea variants, fruit series, and milk series, all of which are adapted to consumer preferences. The organizational structure of this business unit is designed to be functional and efficient, involving the business owner as the strategic decision-maker and operational staff responsible for technical services and maintaining product quality.

By optimizing strategically accessible locations and implementing competitive pricing strategies, Teh Poci Gana strives to sustain its business through responsive service and guaranteed product hygiene, thereby maintaining customer loyalty amid competition in the food and beverage industry.

Description of Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

No.	Characteristics	Classification	Frequency
1	Gender	Male	85
		Female	115
	Total		200
2	Age	16-20	25
		21-25	162
		26-30	10

		>30	3
	Total		200
3	Occupation	Student	192
		Civil Servant	5
		Private Employee	1
		Entrepreneur	2
		Others	0
	Total		200
4	Purchase of Matcha Series	Have Purchased	173
		Have Not Purchased	27
	Total		200

Source: Processed primary data, 2026.

Based on the survey results presented in Table 1, the majority of respondents were female, totaling 115 individuals (57.5%), while male respondents accounted for 85 individuals (42.5%). In terms of age distribution, most respondents were aged 21–25 years, amounting to 162 individuals (81%), followed by those aged 16–20 years with 25 individuals (12.5%), 26–30 years with 10 individuals (5%), and above 30 years with 3 individuals (1.5%).

The majority of respondents were also relatively young, with most being students, totaling 192 individuals (96%). Civil servants accounted for 5 individuals (2.5%), entrepreneurs for 2 individuals (1%), private employees for 1 individual (0.5%), and no respondents fell outside the listed occupational categories.

Furthermore, the survey results indicate that the majority of respondents, 173 individuals (86.5%), had purchased the matcha series product at least once, while 27 respondents (13.5%) had never purchased the matcha series product.

Description of Research Variables

Description of Respondents' Answers on Purchase Decision

Based on the respondents' data, the purchase decision variable obtained an average score of 3.79, which falls into the “agree” category. This indicates that, in general, respondents agree that their decision to purchase Teh Poci Gana products is based on rational considerations, such as cleanliness and quality, as well as emotional aspects such as brand trust and personal preference. Therefore, the current strategies implemented are considered sufficiently effective in encouraging purchase decisions.

Description of Respondents' Answers on Product Innovation

Based on the respondents' data, the product innovation variable obtained an average score of 3.41, which falls into the “agree” category. This suggests that, overall, product innovation at Teh Poci Gana is considered relatively strong. Although each new menu introduced is generally accepted by consumers, improvements are still needed in maintaining consistency in color and taste, as well as enhancing uniqueness, creativity, and product presentation to better compete with competitors.

Description of Respondents' Answers on Social Media Marketing

Based on the respondents' data, the social media marketing variable obtained an average score of 3.36, which falls into the “agree” category. This indicates that, overall, social media promotion is considered fairly effective. Although consumers can

easily find and access information about Teh Poci Gana through Instagram and are interested in visiting, the content quality should be continuously improved to ensure that it more effectively influences consumers' purchase decisions.

Description of Respondents' Answers on Location

Based on the respondents' data, the location variable obtained an average score of 3.42, which falls into the "high" category. This indicates that, in general, the selection of locations that are easily visible and accessible, along with adequate parking capacity, significantly influences consumers' decisions to visit and make purchases. However, environmental cleanliness at the selling locations should be improved to enhance customer comfort, and location selection should continue to ensure optimal market coverage.

Classical Assumption Test Results

Normality Test

Table 2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test

		Unstandardized Residual	
N		200	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000	
	Std. Deviation	2.36009077	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.052	
	Positive	.050	
	Negative	-.052	
Test Statistic		.052	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c		.200 ^d	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^e	Sig		.213
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	.202
		Upper Bound	.223

Source: Processed data, 2026

Table 2 shows that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is 0.200. This value is greater than the significance level (alpha) of 0.05, indicating that the data used in this study are normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

Collinearity Statistics			
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	X1	.806	1.241
	X2	.825	1.212
	X3	.833	1.201
Dependent Variable: Y			

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 3, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values are all below 10, namely 1.241 for X1 (product innovation), 1.212 for X2 (social media marketing), and 1.201 for X3 (location). Additionally, the tolerance values are all above 0.10, namely 0.806 for X1, 0.825 for X2, and 0.833 for X3. Therefore, it can be concluded that the independent variables are free from multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.298	.619		3.711	.000
	X1	-.034	.031	-.085	-1.076	.283
	X2	-.015	.031	.039	.491	.624
	X3	-.001	.027	-.003	-.042	.966

Dependent Variable: ABS_RES

Source: Primary data processed, 2026

Based on Table 4, the significance values are greater than 0.05, namely 0.283 for X1, 0.624 for X2, and 0.966 for X3. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	10.338	1.120		9.233	.000
	X1	.187	.057	.229	3.317	.001
	X2	.122	.056	.150	2.195	.029
	X3	.197	.049	.273	4.009	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Primary data processed, 2026

The multiple linear regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = a + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3$$

$$Y = 10,338 + 0,187 + 0,122 + 0,197$$

The interpretation of the regression model is as follows:

1. The constant value is 10.338, indicating that when product innovation, social media marketing, and location (X1, X2, and X3) are equal to zero, the purchase decision (Y) is 10.338.
2. The coefficient of product innovation (X1) is 0.187, meaning that a 1% increase or decrease in product innovation will lead to an increase or decrease in purchase decisions by 0.187 (18.7%).
3. The coefficient of social media marketing (X2) is 0.122, indicating that a 1% change will affect purchase decisions by 0.122 (12.2%).
4. The coefficient of location (X3) is 0.197, meaning that a 1% change will affect purchase decisions by 0.197 (19.7%).

Partial Significance Test (t-test)

Table 6. t-test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	10.338	1.120		9.233	.000
	X1	.187	.057	.229	3.317	.001
	X2	.122	.056	.150	2.195	.029
	X3	.197	.049	.273	4.009	.000

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 6, the results can be explained as follows:

1. The significance value for product innovation (X1) is 0.001, which is less than 0.05. Thus, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, indicating that product innovation has a positive effect on purchase decisions.
2. The significance value for social media marketing (X2) is 0.029, which is less than 0.05. Thus, H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted, indicating that social media marketing has a positive effect on purchase decisions.
3. The significance value for location (X3) is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Thus, H_0 is rejected and H_3 is accepted, indicating that location has a positive effect on purchase decisions.

Model Feasibility Test (F-test)

Table 7. F-test (ANOVA)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	359.484	3	119.828	21.189	.000 ^b
	Residual	1108.436	196	5.655		
	Total	1467.920	199			

Dependent Variable: Y

Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 7, the significance value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, H_0 is rejected and H_4 is accepted, indicating that product innovation (X1), social media marketing (X2), and location (X3) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions (Y).

Coefficient of Determination (R² Test)

Table 8. R² Test

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.495 ^a	.245	.233	2.378	

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1

Source: Processed data, 2026

For models with more than one independent variable, the Adjusted R Square value is used. The result shows an Adjusted R Square of 0.233. This indicates that product innovation (X1), social media marketing (X2), and location (X3) explain 23.3% of the variation in purchase decisions (Y), while the remaining 76.7% is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

Discussion of Research Findings

The Effect of Product Innovation on Purchase Decision

The results of the first hypothesis (H1) testing indicate that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. Statistically, this is evidenced by a t-test significance value of 0.001, which is far below the significance level of 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$). In addition, the regression coefficient for product innovation is positive at 0.187, indicating that any increase in product innovation contributes significantly to an increase in purchase decisions.

The high level of acceptance of product innovation aligns with the characteristics of the majority of Teh Poci Gana consumers, who are predominantly aged 21–25 years and mostly students. This demographic group represents dynamic consumers who are adaptive to trends and inclined to explore new products. This conclusion is supported by the descriptive analysis of the product innovation variable, which falls into the “agree” category with an average score of 3.41. The fact that most respondents have purchased the Matcha Series further confirms that consumers actively respond to menu innovations.

These findings empirically confirm the effectiveness of the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) theory, which serves as the theoretical foundation of this study. Product innovation, in the form of unique flavors and menu variations not offered by competitors, acts as a strong external stimulus (S). This stimulus is cognitively processed by the organism (O), namely consumers (students), who seek relevance with current trends. This internal process ultimately triggers a positive response (R), manifested in actual purchase decisions.

This finding is consistent with previous studies, such as Lee et al. (2024), which demonstrate that consumers highly value product novelty, significantly increasing purchase decisions. Similarly, Rayi and Aras (2021) argue that higher product innovation quality has a positive and significant influence on consumers’ purchase decisions.

The Effect of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Decision

The results of the second hypothesis (H2) testing indicate that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. This is statistically supported by a t-test significance value of 0.029, which is lower than 0.05 ($0.029 < 0.05$). Furthermore, the regression coefficient for social media marketing is positive at 0.122, indicating that more intensive and effective social media marketing leads to a 12.2% increase in purchase decisions.

This finding is highly relevant to the demographic profile of Teh Poci Gana consumers, who are predominantly young individuals aged 21–25 years and mostly students. This group is highly engaged with digital devices and relies heavily on social media particularly Instagram as a primary reference before making purchasing decisions. The variable falls within the “agree” category, with an average score of 3.36.

Although the completeness of content information is still perceived as suboptimal, the visual accessibility of content successfully attracts consumer interest.

This phenomenon can also be explained through the S-O-R theory. The accessibility and visual design of promotional content on Instagram act as external stimuli (S). These stimuli are processed by the organism (O), namely consumers who are highly receptive to social media trends. The visual appeal shapes their perceptions and builds brand awareness, ultimately triggering a positive response (R) in the form of purchase decisions.

These findings are consistent with previous research by Rahmasari et al. (2023), which states that purchase decisions are significantly influenced by social media marketing, where accessible and engaging content encourages consumer decisions. Similarly, Ahmadi et al. (2024) conclude that social media marketing has a strong positive correlation with purchase decisions, where increased social media usage leads to higher purchase decisions.

The Effect of Location on Purchase Decision

The results of the third hypothesis (H3) testing indicate that location has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. This is evidenced by a t-test significance value of 0.000, which is far below 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Additionally, the regression coefficient for location is positive at 0.197, indicating that more strategic, visible, and accessible locations lead to a 19.7% increase in purchase decisions.

The strong influence of location is rational when linked to the characteristics of Teh Poci Gana consumers, who are predominantly young students with high mobility around campus areas and a preference for convenience and time efficiency. This is supported by the descriptive analysis of the location variable, which falls within the “agree” category with an average score of 3.42. These findings empirically confirm that store placement in strategic locations, such as main roads or intersections, effectively reduces time and effort for consumers, thereby encouraging them to make purchases.

From a theoretical perspective, these findings reinforce the application of the S-O-R theory in the context of physical marketing. Strategic store location, high visibility, and ease of access serve as strong environmental stimuli (S) for passersby. These stimuli are internally processed by the organism (O), namely consumers who perceive convenience and accessibility. This perception of efficiency ultimately triggers a direct response (R), leading to purchase decisions.

This result is consistent with previous studies by Febrianto and Sumaryanto (2024), which state that purchase decisions are significantly influenced by location, particularly due to its visibility. Similarly, Sari and Hidayat (2020) emphasize that easily accessible and clearly visible locations simplify consumers’ decision-making processes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion presented in the previous sections, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. This indicates that higher levels of product innovation lead to increased purchase decisions among consumers.
2. Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. This indicates that more effective social media promotion leads to higher purchase decisions among consumers.
3. Location has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at Teh Poci Gana. This indicates that better and more strategic store locations contribute to increased purchase decisions among consumers.

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